

Studies on the Determination and Distribution of Potassium, Uranium, and Cobalt in Sea Water*

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A report has been made of the determination and distribution of potassium, uranium, and cobalt in sea water. An argentimetric method is recommended for the determination of potassium after precipitating the element as potassium tetraphenylboron (KTPB). An acid-base titration of the KTPB is also discussed; this method, however has a slightly higher coefficient of variation and is more time-consuming.

Surface sea water samples from the Arabian Sea have been analysed for content of uranium. The uranium values range from 1.39 to 4.47 $\mu\text{g./litre}$ with an average of 2.56 $\mu\text{g./litre}$.

For exchangeable cobalt, the possibilities would appear to be present to coprecipitate the element from one litre of sea water and to determine the cobalt in the precipitate on the basis of the Co-59 (α , γ) Co-60 reaction.

The major ions present in sea water are sodium and chloride which constitute 10.56% and 18.98% respectively of the total¹. In addition, sea water contains conservative minor elements like potassium and "trace elements", such as iron, copper, cobalt, etc. Since many of these elements are accumulated by marine organisms in considerable amounts² and have radioactive isotopes with low permissible concentrations in sea water, an understanding of their distribution in the marine environment becomes essential. In the present communication three elements, viz., potassium, uranium, and cobalt, have been selected for study with reference to their distribution in the Arabian Sea and improved methods for their analysis. Of these, potassium contributes most (4.6×10^{11} curies through its content of radioisotope K-40) to natural radioactivity in the sea³. Uranium plays an important role in the geochemical and biochemical cycles in the sea⁴⁻⁵ though not much has been reported about its occurrence in the Arabian Sea. Cobalt is widely distributed in marine sediments and organisms⁶.

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1. H. V. Sverdrup, M. W. Johnson, and R. H. Fleming, "The Oceans. Their Physics, Chemistry and General Biology", Prentice Hall, Inc., N. J., 1957.
2. R. Revelle and M. B. Schaefer, "General Consideration concerning the Ocean as Receptacle for Artificially Radioactive Materials" in "The effects of atomic radiation on oceanography and fisheries". Publication No. 551, National Academy of Sciences—National Research Council, Washington, 1957.
3. T. R. Folsom and J. H. Harley, "Comparison of some natural radiation received by selected organisms" in "The effects of atomic radiation on oceanography and fisheries". Publication No. 551, National Academy of Sciences, National Research Council, Washington, 1961.
4. F. F. Koczy, "Deep Sea Research", Vol III, pp. 93-103, 1956.
5. K. Rankama and Th. G. Sahama, "Geochemistry", University of Chicago Press, Chicago, 1950.
6. L. G. Sillen, "Physical Chemistry of Sea Water" in "Oceanography" (Ed.) Mary Sears, Pub. No. 67. American Association for the Advancement of Science, Washington D. C., 1961

EXPERIMENTAL

Potassium

The tetraphenylboron (TPB) method, described by Sporek⁷, is very specific for the estimation of potassium in sea water and is based on the precipitation and weighing of potassium as potassium tetraphenylboron (KTPB). In view of the titrimetric possibilities of the TPB procedure for potassium⁸ and the obvious advantages of volumetric over gravimetric methods, it was decided to investigate the volumetric estimation of potassium in sea water by argentimetric and acid-base titrations of KTPB.

Reagents.—1% Aqueous solution of sodium tetraphenylboron was made alkaline with a few drops of *N*-NaOH and stored at 0°. The reagent remained stable for about 3 days. It can be stored for a longer period if alumina is added to it and the solution filtered. The wash solution consisted of a clear, saturated aqueous solution of KTPB.

Precipitation of Potassium.—Sea water (10 ml) was acidified with HCl (conc., 0.5 ml), cooled in ice at 0°, and to it 5 ml of TPB reagent (precooled at 0°) was added and it was allowed to stand for 15 min. at 0°. The precipitate was filtered on a 9 cm Whatman No. 42 filter paper and washed till free of chloride and excess TPB ions.

Volumetric Estimation: (a). Argentimetry.—To the KTPB precipitate, dissolved in about 50 ml of acetone, 5 ml of *N*/20 silver nitrate was added. After the addition of 1 ml of 8*M*-HNO₃ and dilution to about 100 ml, the solution was titrated with *N*/20 ammonium thiocyanate solution, using ferric alum as indicator.

$$[\text{mg. K in aliquot} = (\text{ml AgNO}_3 \times N\text{-AgNO}_3 - \text{ml NH}_4 \text{ CNS} \times N\text{-NH}_4 \text{ CNS}) \times 39.1]$$

(b). Acid-base Titration after Cation Exchange.—To the KTPB precipitate, dissolved in 20 ml of acetone, 20 ml of water was added. The solution was then passed through a cation-exchange column (Dowex 50×8, H⁺ form, 50-100 mesh; 0.5×15 cm column equilibrated with 1:1 acetone water) at the rate of 0.5 ml/min. The effluent was titrated with *N*/50-NaOH solution, using Methyl red as indicator. A blank was run by passing a mixture of 20 ml of acetone and 20 ml of water through the column and titrating the effluent with NaOH solution. [mg. K in aliquot = (ml *N*-NaOH) × 39.1].

Effects of Varying the Volume of TPB Reagent.—With a test aliquot of artificial sea water (prepared according to Lyman and Fleming⁹) containing 3.893 mg. of potassium, the recoveries in 6 experiments ranged from 3.879 to 3.902 mg. of potassium (mean, 3.889 mg.; coefficient of variation, 0.25) when the volume of TPB reagent was varied from 5 to 30 ml. Variations in the volume of TPB reagent in the range 5 to 30 ml did not therefore affect the accuracy of the estimation, an observation which was in agreement with that made for standard potassium solutions by Sporek and Williams¹⁰.

Comparison of Methods (a) and (b).—A sea-water sample, collected near Canada India Reactor Jetty, Bombay Harbour Bay on 21-1-63, was analysed by methods (a) and

7. *Analyst*, 1956, **81**, 540.

8. H. Flaschka, and A. J. Barnard Jr., "Tetraphenylboron as an Analytical Reagent" in "Advances in Analytical Chemistry," Vol. 1, (Ed) Charles Reilley. Interscience Publishers, New York, 1960.

9. *J. Marine Res.*, 1940, **3**, 134.

10. *Analyst*, 1935, **60**, 347.

(b). The mean values of ten replicate analyses by each of the methods were identical (0.360 $\mu\text{g./ml}$).

Data from the analyses by methods (a) and (b) of artificial sea water containing varying amounts of added potassium indicated that the standard error was the same, 0.01, for both the methods though the coefficient of variation differed (0.83 in acid-base titration method and 0.36 in argentimetry).

For routine work, however, the argentimetric titration is preferable since it has a better precision and is less time-consuming than the acid-base titration after cation exchange, which involves regeneration of resin, washing of the resin column, etc.

Potassium Content of Surface Sea Water from the Arabian Sea.—Surface sea-water samples, collected during the cruises of I.N.S. Kistna of the International Indian Ocean Expedition, were analysed for potassium by the volumetric KTPB method. The results in Table I are based on analyses of 90 samples from the Arabian Sea (Lat. 7-24° N, Long. 55-74° E, Sep.—Dec. 1962).

TABLE I

Frequency distribution of potassium content of surface sea water in the Arabian Sea.

Range ($\mu\text{g./ml}$).	Frequency (No. of samples).	Average value ($\mu\text{g./ml}$).
250—300	7	286
300—350	7	328
350—400	65	369
400—450	8	426
450—500	3	471

Weighted average = 368 $\mu\text{g./ml}$.

Uranium

For the estimation of uranium, a fluorimetric method, essentially similar to that described by Sandell¹¹, was used. A sample of filtered sea water (500 ml) was acidified to 0.1N in HNO_3 . The uranium was coprecipitated as the phosphate with aluminium phosphate at pH 5.0 and was then extracted with ethyl acetate in *M*- HNO_3 medium with aluminium nitrate as a salting-out agent. A suitable aliquot of the extract, free from water droplets, was evaporated on a platinum planchet and the uranium was determined fluorimetrically, using a Jarrel-Ash fluorimeter. Blanks were run to allow for uranium content of reagents used. Recovery of uranium added to sea water was $95 \pm 5\%$.

The uranium content of surface sea-water samples from the Arabian Sea is recorded in Table II in the form of a frequency distribution.

Of interest were the observations of uniformly high uranium values along the longitude 62°E and near the mouth of the River Indus. These regions would appear to merit more detailed investigation.

11. "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", Interscience Publications Inc., New York, 1959.

TABLE II

Range ($\mu\text{g./litre}$).	Frequency (No. of samples).	Average value ($\mu\text{g./litre}$).
1.00—1.50	1	1.39
1.50—2.00	16	1.74
2.00—2.50	27	2.27
2.50—3.00	27	2.77
3.00—3.50	9	3.25
3.50—4.00	3	3.77
4.00—4.60	4	4.20

Weighted average = $2.56 \mu\text{g./litre} = 0.88861 \mu\text{g./litre}$ of α -activity.

Cobalt

Most of the methods used in the estimation of cobalt in sea water are spectrophotometric and involve the use of large volumes of sea water (100 litres)². Since the promising new tool of radioactivation analysis¹³ was not applied before for the estimation of cobalt in sea water, an attempt was made to concentrate the element from sea water by coprecipitation and to estimate the cobalt in the precipitate γ -spectroscopically on the basis of the Co-59 (n, γ) Co-60 reaction.

Precautions common to trace-element analysis were taken in regard to the reagents used. Distilled water, HNO_3 , and HCl were redistilled in Pyrex glass units. Disodium hydrogen phosphate was purified by repeated extraction with 0.10% dithizone in CCl_4 .

To one litre of filtered sea water, adjusted to pH 8.0, a 25% aqueous solution of disodium hydrogen phosphate was added with stirring to a final phosphate concentration of 0.3%. The precipitate was allowed to settle overnight and was separated on the centrifuge. It was dissolved in the minimum amount of 0.5 *N*- HNO_3 and the solution was passed through a Dowex 50 \times 8, 50-100 mesh, 1.5 \times 25 cm ion-exchange column at the rate of 1 ml/min. 6*N*- HCl (150 ml) was run through the column to elute the cobalt. The phosphate-free effluent containing Co, Fe, etc. was evaporated on a hot plate to a volume of 60-70 ml. HCl (conc., 150 ml) was added to it to make the acid concentration 10 *N*. The acid solution was passed through a Dowex 1 \times 8, 50-100 mesh, 0.7 \times 24 cm ion-exchange column (in the chloride form) at the rate of 1 ml/min. (vide Kraus and Moore¹⁴). Cobalt was eluted from the column by the use of 70 ml of 4*N*- HCl *. The eluate was evaporated to dryness and the residue taken up in a plastic tube and irradiated for 24 hr. in a neutron flux of $10^8 \text{ n/cm}^2/\text{sec}$. Further purification of cobalt was carried out by extraction with α -nitroso- β -naphthol, as described by Sandell¹¹. After reducing the volume of the material by heating with HNO_3 (and incidentally destroying the organic material), the residue was taken up in 1:1 HNO_3 and counted in a γ spectrometer [3" \times 3" NaI (Tl) well type crystal in conjunction with a 10-channel or single channel analyser].

*Elution volumes in all these experiments were determined by conventional methods such as have been described by Samuelson¹⁵.

12. Weiss and Reed, *J. Marine Res.*, 1959, 16, 186.

13. R. Fukai and W. W. Meinke, "Limnology and Oceanography", Vol. 4, pp. 398-408, 1959.

14. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 75, 1460.

15. "Ion Exchangers in Analytical Chemistry", Wiley, New York, 1953.

For calculating the efficiency of the separation procedure, known amounts of Co-60 were added to sea water, treated with phosphate, and passed through ion-exchanger prior to counting. Recovery data are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

Expt. No.	Activity of Co-60 (counts/min.).		% Recovery.
	Added.	Recovered.	
1	534	500	93.4
2	534	446	83.5
3	526	488	91.4
4	475	433	91.2
			Mean 89.9

Results in Table III suggest that relatively small size sea-water samples (1 litre) would suffice for the estimation of exchangeable cobalt in sea water if the element is first concentrated by coprecipitation, separated from other elements (to minimise extra activity on irradiation) by ion exchange, and then subjected to a neutron flux. This would be a distinct advantage in the study of problems such as the horizontal and vertical distribution of cobalt and the distribution of the element in the ionic and particulate phases in sea water.

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